

POLITENESS IN POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE CONTEXTS

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Abstract: The aim of the work is studying the linguistic and cultural characteristics of politeness and giving a deeper understanding of the cultural values and behavior patterns of people. Also highlights linguacultural characteristics of expressing politeness and it allows us to better understand the differences and similarities between cultures in any languages.

Key words: politeness, positive politeness, negative politeness, communicating, interactions.

Politeness refers to a set of social behaviors and language forms that people use to show respect, avoid conflict, and maintain positive relationships with others. It helps smooth social interactions by allowing individuals to express themselves in ways that minimize potential offense or discomfort at the same time politeness as a social phenomenon is of great importance in intercultural communication. Politeness as a characteristic of communicative behavior has repeatedly become the object of scientific study by linguists, however, there are a number of aspects associated with the category of politeness that deserve more detailed consideration. In particular, a sufficiently complete definition of the concept of “politeness” has not yet been formulated and a whole layer of vocabulary that reflects different types and tools of polite human behavior has not been described.

When we look through its meaning the most successful description of the word politely (and its synonyms gallantly, politely, kindly) is offered by

T.V. Krylova: “Politely” – demonstrating in the form established by etiquette a respectful and benevolent attitude towards another person and pleasure from communicating with him. According to this interpretation, polite behavior consists in demonstrating a certain attitude towards a person established by etiquette

– “respectful” and “benevolent”, as well as pleasure from communicating with this person.” According to the explanatory dictionary of D.V. Dmitriev, politeness is the quality of a polite person, a set of good manners, the ability to behave in society [4; 624]. Each language and culture has its own unique ways of expressing politeness, which depend on the cultural and historical characteristics of the people.

These social interactions can be diversified and are not restricted to politeness in the common meaning of the word. The purpose of politeness often

revolves around maintaining “face” a term used to describe a person’s social identity or self-esteem. According to sociolinguists Penelope Brown and Stephen Levinson, politeness helps individuals manage “face-threatening acts” (actions or language that could damage someone's social standing). In the broadest sense, they can be separated into two types: positive and negative politeness, as defined by Patricia Brown and Stephen Levinson, who expanded on Erving Hoffman’s theories about the “social face”. Brown and Levinson suggests the theory of politeness by considering the concepts of positive and negative face as key components of politeness [1].

Positive face is associated with the desire to be accepted and recognized, while negative face reflects the desire for independence and respect for personal boundaries. When the asker uses terms that are similar to those in the following question (A), they are able to attract the other person to a joint goal and friendship as well. This is the consequence of the technique of positive politeness. As an example, we may analyze the following dialogue:

A. How about letting him see her gift?

B. Hello, friend, he'd be glad if she'd let him see her gift.

These expressions, in fact, indicate an elevated risk to the speaker who is subjected to a rejection and can be led by a number of individuals who want to understand you when you speak, similar to the kind that is displayed in the following, which is designed to establish the necessary common on the basis of this strategy.

- Hello. How’s it going?

- Ok, if I sit there? We should be interested in the same crazy things. You take a lot of remarks as well, huh? Say, do me a big favor and let me take one of your pencils.

Nevertheless, mainly in nearly all the contexts of English speaking, the action of face saving is usually done by means of a strategy of negative politeness. The usual shape utilized is a question that includes a modal verb like the following (A):

A. Could you lend me a pencil?

B. I am sorry to bother you, but can I ask you for a pencil or something?

C. I know you're busy, but might I ask you if-me-if you happen to have an additional pencil that I can, you know –eh- borrow?

Utilizing this strategy leads to structures including apology expressions for imposing the kind seen in (B). Further complex negative politeness action may from time to time be listened to in extensive chat, frequently with uncertainties, the same as in (B) [3]. Negative politeness is usually articulated by questions

which even request agreement to pose, for instance, might we ask? as seen in (C). Superficially, questions like these provide a chance for another to reply in negative manner to the question without embracing the same effect of refusal of replying with negativity to a bald straight on record imperative [2; 4-5].

Politeness is strongly dependent on the structure of hierarchical relations in society as well as the social distance that exists between the speaker and other people. Also, politeness is associated with the linguistic expression of solidarity, the inclusion of the interlocutor and other individuals who are in the same group as the speaker, whereas negative politeness is associated with the self-restraint of the speakers, the desire to avoid conflicts or disagreements. These social relations can be diverse and are far from being limited to politeness in the colloquial sense of the word.

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